

DISTINCTIONS BETWEEN BIOCHEMICAL INDICATORS OF DIFFERENT BLOOD GROUPS

¹Azizova N.M., ¹Yuldashev N.M., ²Saidov A.B.

¹Tashkent pediatric medical institute

²Republic blood transfusion center

Resume. The purpose of this work is to evaluate the differences in some biochemical parameters in blood plasma of blood groups I (0), II (A), III (B) and IV (AB). Biochemical indicators were determined on a Humastar100 (Germany) biochemical analyzer. The obtained results showed that there are certain statistically reliable differences between the amounts of biochemical indicators such as albumin, glucose, cholesterol, triglyceride and urea in blood plasmas of different blood groups.

Key words: ABO system, blood plasma, total protein, albumin, glucose, triglyceride, cholesterol, urea, creatinine.

The purpose of research. Evaluation of differences between biochemical indicators of erythrocytes of different blood groups.

Material and methods. Biochemical indicators were determined on a Humastar100 (Germany) biochemical analyzer. The obtained results showed that there are certain statistically reliable differences between the amounts of biochemical indicators such as albumin, glucose, cholesterol, triglyceride and urea in blood plasmas of different blood groups.

Analysis of the obtained results. Biochemical indicators in blood plasma of different blood groups are presented. The obtained results showed that the amount of total protein in blood plasmas of different blood groups did not differ from each other. The amount of protein varied from 57 g/l to 70 g/l. There was a tendency to decrease in the amount of albumin in blood group 0 (I), and to increase in blood group B (III) and AB (IV).

Despite the fact that the amount of glucose in blood groups 0 (I) and A (II) was for 18.2 and 22.5% higher than in the general group, this difference was statistically insignificant. In B (III) and AB (IV) blood groups, compared to the general group, on the contrary, the amount of glucose decreased by 19.0 and 21.9%, but this decrease was not statistically reliable either. At the same time, the amount of glucose in group AB (IV) was statistically significantly lower by 36.3% compared to group A (II).

Cholesterol content in plasma of A (II) blood group was for 14.8 and 23.4% lower than total and 0 (I) blood groups statistically reliably, respectively.

When the amount of triglycerides in the plasma of different blood groups was studied, amount in AB (IV) blood group was for 27.4, 32.1, 32.1, 33.5% in 0 (I), 0 (I), A (II) and B (III) blood groups.

No statistically reliable changes were detected between the compared groups in the level of molybdenum in the plasma of different blood groups. At the same time, the absolute amount of urea was the highest in blood group A (II).

And finally, the study of the amount of creatinine in the blood plasma of different blood groups did not show significant differences in the amount of this substance between the compared blood groups.

We also calculated the amount of biochemical indicators studied above in relation to 1 erythrocyte. The reason for this is that 1 liter of blood usually does not contain a specific number of erythrocytes, that is, even if there is a little difference in their number, a difference is observed. Amounts of biochemical parameters in blood plasma of different blood groups calculated per 1 erythrocyte are presented.

The obtained results showed that the amount of total protein in blood plasmas of different blood groups did not differ from each other. Protein content ranged from 13.48 g/RBC to 17.07 g/RBC.

The decrease of albumin amount in plasma was not statistically reliable when calculated. When the amount of albumin was calculated per 1 erythrocyte, it was found that it was statistically reliably decreased by 10.8% in blood group 0 (I)

compared to the general group. The amount of albumin calculated per erythrocyte in blood group B (III) plasma was statistically reliably higher by 20.7% compared to blood group 0 (I).

When the amount of glucose in the plasma of different blood groups was calculated per 1 erythrocyte, the amount of glucose in blood groups A (II) was statistically reliably 24.8% higher than in the general group. When the amount of glucose is calculated per 1 erythrocyte, its amount in AB (IV) blood group was statistically reliably lower by 37.8% compared to A (II) blood group.

The amount of cholesterol in A (II) blood group, calculated per 1 erythrocyte, was 13.8 and 21.1% lower in comparison with the total and 0 (I) blood groups, respectively. When calculated for 1 erythrocyte, the amount of cholesterol in erythrocytes of group B (III) was statistically reliably higher by 22.7% compared to group A (II).

When the amount of triglycerides in the plasma of different blood groups is calculated per 1 erythrocyte, the total amount of triglycerides in blood group AB (IV), in groups 0 (I), A (II) and B (III) is statistically reliably 26.2, 29.6, 31.1 and 31.1%.

When calculated in relation to 1 erythrocyte, the amount of urea in blood group A (II) was statistically significantly higher than the amount in groups 0 (I) by 18.3 and 29.2%, respectively.

Finally, the study of creatinine amount in the blood plasma of different blood groups in relation to 1 erythrocyte did not show significant differences in the amount of this substance between the compared blood groups.

Summary. Thus, the studies conducted showed that there are certain statistically reliable differences between the amounts of a number of biochemical indicators such as albumin, glucose, cholesterol, triglyceride and urea in the blood plasma belonging to different groups according to the ABO system. These results allow in the future to determine the normal limits of biochemical parameters,

taking into account the blood group approach, as well as to individualize the normal values of biochemical parameters.